

EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE OF STRATEGIC DIMENSIONS ON THE REBRANDING PERFORMANCE OF POWER SECTOR IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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Keywords:

Strategic Dimensions, Rebranding performance, implantation analysis, low-cost strategy, net promoter score and net profit margin.

Abstract: *This study examined influence of strategic dimensions on the rebranding performance of power sector in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives include the following to: examine the extent to which implementation strategy influence on net promoter score of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria and ascertain the extent to which low-cost strategy influence on net profit margin of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria. The researcher employed survey research design. Structured questionnaire was used. The population of the study was infinite, while the sample size of 384 was drawn, using Topman formula. Based on the data collected and analyzed with regression Analytical method, the study found that; implementation strategy had significant positive influence on net promoter score of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria. This is confirmed with regression result; ($t\text{-cal} = 165.015$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05\%$) and low-cost strategy had significant positive influence on net profit margin of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria. This is confirmed with regression result ($t\text{-cal} = 36.318$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05\%$). Therefore, the study concluded that strategic dimensions had significant positive influence on the rebranding performance of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study recommended that for every power supply firm in Enugu State to succeed and stay afloat, managers should incorporate a robust implementation strategy in their plan due to its positive effect on net promoter score and in order to enjoy high patronage from customers and operate profitably too, power supply firms in Enugu State should adopt low-cost strategy because of its positive effect on net profit margin.*

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of power sector reform in Nigeria cannot be overstated, particularly in the context of fostering industrialization. Nigeria's industrial sector has long been hindered by chronic power shortages and unreliable electricity supply, impeding the growth and competitiveness of industries. Power sector reform is imperative to address this issue and unlock the full potential of

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industrialization (Ahumibe, Olewe & Nze, 2024). According to the World Bank, inadequate and unreliable power supply has been a major constraint on Nigeria's industrial development (World Bank, 2019).

Once upon a time, the Oji River coal-fired generating plant supplied power to much of the former Eastern Region through the Electricity Corporation of Nigeria (ECN). Today, following sector reforms initiated in 2005 via the Electric Power Sector Reform Act, 2005 the State's electricity customers are served by Enugu Electricity Distribution Company Limited (Enugu Disco or EEDC). Enugu Disco was created out of the Enugu Zone of the defunct National Electric Power Authority and was privatised in 2013, with a core investor, Eastern Electric Limited, taking over 60% equity and management control of the company (Ahumibe, Olewe & Nze, 2024).

Uniquely, Enugu Disco is the only Disco in Nigeria that serves a single geopolitical zone, the South-East. Unfortunately, however, this has brought no real benefit to the people of Enugu State since capacity and energy delivered to the entire national grid have stagnated since 2015 at an average 4GW/96GWh daily, of which Enugu Disco receives an allocation of 9% or an average 360MW/8,640MWh daily. This breaks down further to approximately 69MW//1656MWh daily for Enugu State or 13.5 watts or 324watt-hours per capita per day, just enough to power three 10-watt LED bulbs for approximately 10 hours a day or a single 10-watt bulb for slightly more than 24 hours.

Strategic dimensions are a concept which concerns making decisions and taking corrective actions to achieve long-term targets and goals of an organization or management (Bakar, *et al*, 2021). It is a set of decisions and actions that result in the formulation and implementation of plans designed to achieve a company's objectives (Pearce & Robinson, 2018). The business environment in which firms operate is dynamic and, turbulent with constant and fast paced changes that often render yesteryears strategies irrelevant (Ofunya, 2023).

Strategies should therefore be put in place to cushion the businesses from the uncertainty that comes along with an unpredictable environment. Strategic addresses the reason why some organizations succeed while others fail (Melchorita, 2023). Strategic involves identifying the organization's current mission, objectives and strategies, analyzing the environment, identifying the opportunities and threats, analyzing the organization's resources, identifying the strengths and weaknesses, formulating and implementing strategies and evaluating the results (Robbins & Coulter, 2019).

The concept of branding performance is core to business because the major objective of businesses is to make profits. Rebranding functions as a value creator in the minds of consumers or target markets. This article focuses on the phenomenon of rebranding, as evidenced by the changing characteristics of power supply. Several researchers have conducted scientific investigations on rebranding performance, and strategic dimensions. However, no research has been conducted on the rebranding performance and strategic dimensions of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria, applying the measures of Souiden and Kassim (2022), which include changing brand name corporate image and

rebrand corporate reputation. This is because we intend to empirically validate these measures in a rebranding strategy in a different geographical area.

Therefore, this study applies the brand equity model proposed by Esch *et al.* (2006) as the basic theory for this study. Iravo *et. al* (2022) states that one of the important questions in business has been why some organizations succeed and why others fail and this have influenced a study on the drivers of rebranding performance, Awino (2021) asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. Njihia, *et. al.* (2023) highlight rebranding performance measurement as one of the tools which helps firms in monitoring performance, identifying the areas that need attention, enhancing motivation, improving communication and strengthening accountability.

Statement of the Problem

A reliable and adequate power supply is of paramount importance for industrialization in Enugu State, Nigeria. Industries heavily depend on electricity to power machinery, facilitate production processes, and maintain consistent operations. The absence of a stable power supply has been a longstanding impediment, hindering the growth and competitiveness of the power sector. Inadequate electricity availability leads to increased implementation strategy, low-cost strategy, reduced net profit margin, and constraints on expansion and modernization efforts.

The current state of power sector supply in Nigeria has profound implications for industrialization, acting as a significant bottleneck to the growth and competitiveness of the industrial sector. The persistent challenges of inadequate and unreliable electricity supply have hindered the optimal functioning of industries, impacting their productivity and global competitiveness. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), Nigeria faces severe electricity shortages, with many industries experiencing frequent power outages that disrupt operations and hinder production processes (IEA, 2021).

These disruptions not only lead to increased operational costs, low net promoter score, poor net profit margin but also discourage potential investors from establishing or expanding industrial facilities in the country by using implementation strategy and low-cost strategy. The unreliability of power supply is a major constraint on the overall development of the industrial sector in Nigeria (World Bank, 2019). Based on this backdrop, the study seeks to examine the influence of strategic dimensions on the rebranding performance of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the influence of strategic dimensions on the rebranding performance of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the extent to which implementation strategy influence on net promoter score of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain the extent to which low-cost strategy influence on net profit margin of power supply

in Enugu State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Strategic Dimensions

Oxenfeldt (2022), referred to the strategy concept as involving the selection and evaluation of target market segments. Subsequently, the term strategy has been commonly associated with the various elements of the marketing mix (Oxenfeldt & Moore, 2019) and companies have frequently considered their entire range of pricing, product, distribution and advertising strategies as comprising a wide spectrum of marketing decisions, all of which are labelled “strategic” (Greenley, 2019).

Implementation Strategy

Strategy implementation is the stage where the real action in an organization is executed through the strategic management process (Allio 2022). It is the set of activities where the strategic plan is changed into strict performance in an organization. However, strategic change in planning is important, but the process is a little bit challenging.

Low-Cost Strategy

Optimizing cost is significant in contemporary business operations, especially restaurants, since it is the foundation for maximization of profitability. Kraja and Osmani (2023) explained that low-cost strategies boost firm performance, mostly financial performance.

Rebranding Performance

Sameer (2022) rebranding simply is engaged in by marketing-oriented organizations in order to reposition its organization in the minds of target market as value adding. This includes the process of changing some features and modifying the offerings of an organization in order to revitalize the firm’s position in the minds of customers. Rebranding performance is too often restricted to its financial facet. As a matter of fact, most evaluations of organizational performance are based on indicators such as return on investments, sales, profit per share (Morin, 2019). Performance is the end result of activities carried out and for any business it is concerned with the general efficiency or productivity (Udeh & Oluka, 2024).

Net Promoter Score

Net Promoter Score (NPS) is a metric in the realm of customer experience management, renowned for its simplicity and effectiveness in measuring customer loyalty and satisfaction. Introduced in 2003 by Fred Reichheld of Bain & Company, alongside Satmetrix, NPS has evolved into a universal standard embraced by companies globally to gauge the health of their customer relationships and predict business growth (Udeh & Oluka, 2024).

Net Profit Margin

Net profit margin is the ratio between net income, namely sales after deducting all expenses including taxes compared to sales (Syamsudin, 2017). Net profit margin (NPM), shows the ratio between net profit after tax or net income to total sales. This ratio measures the company's ability to generate net

income against total sales achieved. This ratio shows how much percentage of net income is earned from each sale, the greater this ratio the better because it is considered that the company's ability to earn profits is quite high (Harahap, 2019). Net profit margin (NPM) is also called the ratio of earnings to sales. Net profit margin is equal to net income divided by sales.

Power Supply

The concept of power supply refers to the provision of electrical energy to meet the demands of various consumers, encompassing residential, commercial, and industrial sectors. Power supply systems involve the generation, transmission, and distribution of electricity, ensuring a reliable and constant flow of energy to end-users (Ahumibe, Olewe & Nze, 2024).

Theoretical Framework

Upper echelons theory (UET) was first put forward by Hambrick and Mason (1984) in an attempt to provide a new perspective on the two prevailing questions of organisational theory: (1) why organisations act as they do, and (2) why organisations perform the way they do. Upper echelons theory (UET) posits that the personal characteristics of TMTs significantly influence their leadership styles, strategic decisions, and, ultimately, organizational outcomes such as sustained performance and competitiveness (Bekos & Chari, 2023). UET emphasizes the role of the leader's observable demographic variables such as age, tenure, education, and experience in shaping strategic choices (Samimi *et al.*, 2022). Based on the UET, these characteristics which serve as proxies for deeper cognitive and behavioural traits are thought to reflect an executive's values, perceptions, and decision-making tendencies, thereby impacting organizational identity and strategic outcomes (Hambrick, 2018).

Empirical Review

Eazal, Muhammad and Asia (2017) determined the operations strategy practices of SMEs. There is a close link between operations strategies and firm performance. The result show that the most preferred competitive priority is cost followed by quality and flexibility delivery priority the least sought-after operations strategy.

Laura (2017) determined the low-cost strategies in the context of global market dynamics. The globalization process has generated an increase of the international competition, far I that influenced the strategies 'adopted by the firms. The purpose of this article is not only to analyse the impact that the relocation of production has on the macroeconomic level, but also to determine the consumers' perceptions and their responses to the challenges generated by this process.

Joseph and Jovee (2018) examined the effect of cost reduction strategies on organization performance: a case of Kenya forest service. The study found out that planned recruitment and training has enhanced the performance of Kenya Forest service through improved operations and reduction of conflict between the staff and members of the public as well as defining the job holder's position.

Olakunle (2018) studied Factors and the Performance of" Micro and Small-Scale Enterprises (MSKs) in Ondo State, Nigeria. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire and analysed

using descriptive statistics and Spearman Correlations. The findings imply that majority of MSEs are chronically under-financed as a result of funding inaccessibility. Results obtained from the joint test showed that environmental factors affected the productivity of SMEs.

Adecko (2017) studied external business environment and entrepreneurial performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The Taro Yamane formula was used to obtain a sample size of 478. Result revealed that infrastructural facilities have a significant and positive effect on SME's service quality ($R^2 = 0.872$; $p = 0.0000.05$). The analysis of insecurity and market growth shows a negative and significant effect of insecurity on SMEs market growth potentials ($R^2 = 6.01$ $p = 0.036$).

Mohammed and Abdullahi (2021) analysed the effect of erratic power supply on the productivity and profitability of small and medium enterprises in A.B.U community market in Samaru Zaria. The research is a cross-sectional survey. A structured questionnaire was used to collect the data for the study. The finding reveals that 90.91% of the enterprises studied indicated that erratic power supply was the major constraint to their productivity and profitability, with an average of 180 hours of power outage per month lasting 6 hours per day, causing the enterprises an average of N24, 000:00 monthly.

Ahmad, *et al* (2023) conducted a study to analyze the impact of electricity supply on the productivity of small-scale industries in Kano metropolis. The model was specified using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Econometric technique. The results show that education, size of business, duration of electricity supplied by Kano Electricity Distribution Company (KEDCO).

Afukonyo (2023) investigated the impact of inadequate power supply on small and medium scale Enterprises: A Case study of Takum Local Government Area of Taraba State. The study also used 30 structured questionnaires to collect primary data directly from the selected SMEs. The study also revealed that epileptic power supply does not affect the operational performance of SMEs and that the supply of power to SMEs is not sufficient.

Ezema-Kalu (2024) examined rebranding strategies and customer patronage of Sammies restaurant in Choba, Port Harcourt, rivers state, Nigeria. This work was an investigation into the impact of a rebranding strategy on the customer patronage of Sammies Restaurant in Choba, Port Harcourt. The research design applied for this study is across-sectional survey design. The findings suggest that changing a company's image and reputation can be a valuable activity in organizations such as fast-food restaurants in Nigeria.

Ahumibe, Olewe & Nze (2024) carried out a study on power supply and industrialization in Enugu State, Nigeria. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 2,299. Taro Yamani formula was used to determine the sample size of 341. The collected data was analyzed through the use of mean score. The findings revealed that Power supply has a significant negative effect on operational costs of industries in Enugu State, Nigeria and that power supply had a significant negative effect on competitiveness of industries in Enugu State, Nigeria (this is where ($2cal = 258.945$, $p = 0.000$).

Gap in Empirical Review

Many extant literatures were reviewed out the country in a different sector and concepts, but the recent study underpinned on empirical evidence of strategic dimensions on the rebranding performance of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria. Little research has been carried out specifically

on strategic management and its influence on the performance of Small-Scale Business in South East Nigeria, based on this, this study was aimed at filling this gap through its findings.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the survey research method. Survey descriptive method was used to plan the study because the researcher did not have direct control or independent methodology or possibly could be manipulated. Opinion of a large population is possible true a small sample which will be engendered by the survey design. The sources of data that used were primary and secondary data sources. The population of the study was the entire customers who patronize EEDC in Enugu State. Therefore, the entire population was unknown while sample size determination showcases 384 using Topman formula. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Bio-data are presented in tables, simple percentages. Analyses of data were done using mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method.

Hypothesis One

Implementation strategy has positive influence on net promoter score of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.993 ^a	.986	.986		.08421

a. Predictors: (Constant), IMPLSTRATEGY

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	193.102	1	193.102	27230.053	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.808	396	.007		
	Total	195.911	397			

a. Dependent Variable: NETPROMOTERSSCORE

b. Predictors: (Constant), IMPLSTRATEGY

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.027	.027		.985	.325
	IMPLSTRATEGY	.997	.006	.993	165.015	.000

a. Dependent Variable: NETPROMOTERSSCORE

The R² (Coefficient of determination):

In the above model, $R^2 = 0.986$, which implies that approximately 99% of the variation in the dependent variable “Net Promoters Score” (NETPROMOTERSSCORE) is caused by the explanatory variable “Implementation Strategy” (IMPLSTRATEGY).

$$\text{NETPOMOTER} = 0.027 + 0.997 (\text{PROMOTER}) + \mu.$$

This test was conducted to ascertain the significant status of each of the parameters or variables. In doing this, we employed the two-tail tests which compared the t-calculated for the explanatory variables with the t-tabulated.

Decision Rule: It states that if the probability value of t-test statistics is greater than 5% margin which is the critical value, the alternative hypotheses would be rejected and the null accepted, but if probability value of t-test statistics is less than 5% margin, the alternative hypothesis would be accepted and the null hypothesis rejected.

Decision:

From the analysis in table 4.16; probability value i.e (t-cal = 165.015, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%). Therefore, we accept alternative hypothesis which states that Implementation strategy has positive influence on net promoter score of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Low-cost strategy has positive influence on net profit margin of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.928 ^a	.861	.860		.26238

a. Predictors: (Constant), LOWCOSTSTRATEGY

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	168.649	1	168.649	2449.816	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.261	396	.069		
	Total	195.911	397			

a. Dependent Variable: NPM

b. Predictors: (Constant), LOWCOSTSTRATEGY

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.627	.080		7.889	.000
	LOWCOSTSTRATEGY	.862	.017	.928	49.496	.000

a. Dependent Variable: NPM

The R² (Coefficient of determination):

In the above model, $R^2 = 0.861$ adjusted to 0.860 , which implies that approximately 84% of the variation in the dependent variable “Net Profit MArgin” (NPM) is caused by the explanatory variable “Low-Cost Strategy” (LOWCOSTSTRATEGY).

$$\text{NETPROFIT} = 0.627 + 0.862 (\text{NETPROFIT}) + \mu.$$

This test was conducted to ascertain the significant status of each of the parameters or variables. In doing this, we employed the two-tail tests which compared the t-calculated for the explanatory variables with the t-tabulated.

Decision Rule: It states that if the probability value of t-test statistics is greater than 5% margin which is the critical value, the alternative hypotheses would be rejected and the null accepted, but if probability value of t-test statistics is less than 5% margin, the alternative hypothesis would be accepted and the null hypothesis rejected.

Decision:

From the analysis in table 4.17; probability value i.e (t-cal = 36.318, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%). Therefore, we accept alternative hypothesis which states that Low-cost strategy has positive influence on net profit margin of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

Based on the data collected and analyzed, the study found that:

- i. Implementation strategy had significant positive influence on net promoter score of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria. This is confirmed with regression result; (t-cal = 165.015, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%).
- ii. Low-cost strategy had significant positive influence on net profit margin of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria. This is confirmed with regression result; (t-cal = 36.318, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05%).

Conclusion

Based on the findings made, the study established thus; those strategic dimensions had significant positive influence on the rebranding performance of power supply in Enugu State, Nigeria. The findings shows that all the indicators used in the study (Implementation strategy and Low-cost strategy) have significant positive influence on the performance of small-scale business in South East Nigeria.

Recommendations

- i. For every power supply firm in Enugu State to succeed and stay afloat, managers should incorporate a robust implementation strategy in their plan due to its positive effect on net promoter score.
- ii. In order to enjoy high patronage from customers and operate profitably too, power supply firms in Enugu State should adopt low-cost strategy because of its positive effect on net profit margin.

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